

Bright Urbanization

Unfolding the potential between DTU and Lyngby

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How can the synergies between DTU and the local community be improved? - How is the interaction facilitated among citizens, companies and students?

As a solution to these questions a new development on the greenfield in Hjortekær, next to DTU and in proximity to Lyngby city center, is presented. The new area, Bright City, is developed as a sustainable hub for R&D companies, students and the inhabitants in Lyngby.

The main focus throughout the entire process has been to enhance the synergy between DTU and Lyngby. The plan is to develop the plot east of the highway next to DTU as a neighbourhood inspired by Silicon Valley where technology and innovation thrives. The Bright City is an area where R&D companies, education and housings are brought together in a sustainable and innovative way. Developing this area will be done by using the newest sustainable technologies and the green areas will be conserved and kept open for the public. Marketing of DTU activities in an open accessible test-site will attract new R&D companies, by sharing knowledge and knowhow to public. To create a flourishing neighbourhood it's important to attract a diverse composition of inhabitants with a focus on attracting the "creative class". Reaching out to this diverse group of people it is important to realise the different personas from the target groups. Target groups include students, families, professors as well as elderly. The Bright City contains a various range of facilities and social events that could fit to all of these personas and make them interact with each other. To reach the different target groups the project has to be advertised through different media such as a website, workshops, social media, posters, local, national and professional newspapers. To make the area interesting for the locals, different social events can be organised e.g. clothes-swapping events, market days, do-it-yourself-workshops and sport activities.